

GAS EXTRACTION DURING THE APOLLO NEXT GENERATION SAMPLE ANALYSIS PROGRAM: POTENTIAL IMPLICATIONS FOR FUTURE SEALED LUNAR SAMPLES. R. A. Zeigler¹ and J. Gross¹. ¹NASA-JSC, Astromaterials Acquisition and Curation Office, 2101 NASA Parkway, Houston, Texas ryan.a.zeigler@nasa.gov.

The ANGSA (Apollo Next Generation Sample Analysis) Program was a consortium of nine different research teams brought together to study a subset of the remaining unopened and specially curated (i.e., frozen) Apollo samples. The program was designed as a multi-generational team using cutting edge techniques to address primary science goals from the Apollo mission not achievable during the Apollo mission phase, as well as to prepare for the upcoming return of samples from the Artemis missions [1-2]. This abstract will focus on the gas extraction work done on sample 73001.

ANGSA samples 73001 and 73002 were collected on the South Massif landslide deposit at the rim of Lara Crater at Station 3 during the second EVA of the Apollo 17 mission [3]. Together 73001/2 are a double drive tube [4], a 4 cm diameter, 70 cm long thin-walled aluminum tube hammered into the surface by the Apollo astronauts. After the double drive tube was removed from the lunar subsurface, the two 35 cm long drive tubes were unscrewed and separated, and each individual drive tube sample was secured for the trip back to Earth. The top half, 73002, was immobilized in its drive tube and returned unsealed. The bottom half, 73001, was first immobilized in its drive tube, and then placed in a secondary stainless-steel (SS) tube that had a metal knife edge seal (Indium-Silver alloy), known as a core sample vacuum container (CSVC). This CSVC [4] was sealed under vacuum on the lunar surface. Both 73001 and 73002 were transported to Earth in Apollo Lunar Sample Return Container (ALSRC) #2 [5].

Upon return to Earth, sample 73001 (in the unopened CSVC) was removed from the ALSRC inside the nitrogen purged processing cabinets, weighed by difference (809 g), and then the CSVC was sealed within a large outer vacuum container (OVC) made of stainless steel that was pumped down to ~10⁻² Torr, which was in turn sealed inside two large Teflon bags. The OVC was placed in special low-vibration nitrogen purged storage in the lunar curation facility. All this work was done in the nitrogen purged cabinets. After the OVC repair, 73001 sat inside its never opened CSVC, repaired OVC, and two outer Teflon bags, undisturbed in low vibration nitrogen purged storage in the lunar vaults until it was removed for gas extraction, XCT analysis, and extrusion/dissection starting in March of 2022.

As part of the ANGSA program, the gas in both the 73001 OVC and CSVC was extracted. The OVC had an external valve in place to help facilitate gas extraction, but the CSVC did not have an external valve. Thus, the CSVC had to be pierced to extract

the gas. Gas extraction was achieved using two bespoke pieces of equipment that were built for the ANGSA project: (1) a gas extraction manifold built by the Team at Washington University in St. Louis led by Drs. Alex Meshik, Olga Pravdivtseva, and Rita Parai; (2) a piercing device built by a team at ESA led by Dr. Francesca McDonald. Gas was extracted from the OVC and CSVC using differential pressure between those containers and the gas extraction manifold, which typically achieved pressures in the mid 10⁻⁹ Torr range (unless otherwise noted). The gas extraction manifold originally had eight ~2-liter SS bottles and two 50 cm³ SS bottles attached to it for storing the extracted gas; a ninth ~1-liter SS bottle was also added to the system before the extraction was completed. See Table 1 for a summary of all gas samples acquired.

Two separate gas extractions from the OVC were done. The initial OVC extraction was done with a background manifold pressure of 4 x 10⁻⁶ Torr, an equilibration time of 15 minutes (all equilibration times are 15 minutes unless otherwise stated), and the gas was expanded into one 2-liter bottle and one 50 cm³ bottle. The equilibration pressure observed on gas sample OVC1 was 28 Torr. Just prior to acquiring gas sample OVC1, a system blank was collected under the sample conditions (e.g., similar background manifold pressure and equilibration time). The second OVC extraction was collected into one 2-liter bottle with a background manifold pressure of 5 x 10⁻⁸ Torr; the gas for OVC2 was passed through a tube sitting in a water ice bath during extraction. The equilibrated pressure on OVC2 was 7 Torr.

After the OVC gas extraction was completed, the OVC was placed back into the N₂-purged curation cabinets, the OVC was opened, the CSVC was removed from the OVC, and the CSVC was sealed within the piercing tool. The piercing tool was then removed from the N₂ purged cabinets and connected to the gas extraction manifold. The piercing tool was then pumped down by the gas extraction manifold prior to piercing the CSVC to remove the N₂ cabinet gas in the piercing tool. During the pump down of the piercing tool over the course of ~48 hours, we were unable to achieve a manifold pressure lower than 10⁻⁶ Torr, whereas we could achieve a vacuum of 10⁻⁹ Torr in the manifold when the piercing tool was isolated. The RGA analysis of the gas being pumped out of the piercing tool was nearly pure N₂ gas and showed no evidence for atmospheric contamination of the system, nor did multiple He-leak checks of the piercing tool and extraction manifold

show evidence of an external leak. Thus, it was decided that there was a slow leak of the CSVC “bleeding” gas out into the piercing tool through the knife edge seal (perhaps representing the de facto leak rate of the CSVC).

The CSVC “leak gas” was accumulated within the piercing tool for ~24 hours and then collected into one 2-liter bottle with a background manifold pressure of 10⁻⁹ Torr (CSVC Leak Gas 1). This process was repeated under almost identical conditions to collect an additional 2-liter bottle of gas as CSVC Leak Gas 2. In both cases, the observed equilibration pressure in the collection bottle for the leak gas samples was ~0.2 Torr. After the CSVC leak gases were collected, the piercing tool was isolated from the manifold, the piercing mechanism on the piercing tool was successfully used to pierce the bottom of the stainless steel CSVC (making a ~2 mm hole), and a first gas extraction from the pierced CSVC was collected in two 2-liter bottles and one 50 cm³ bottle with an equilibration pressure of 4.6 Torr. A second longer gas extraction (CSVC extraction 2) was performed with an equilibration time of 10.75 days, with a final equilibration pressure of 3.2 Torr. Finally, the gas extraction manifold was used to pump down the CSVC/piercing tool to a pressure of 2 x 10⁻⁷ Torr. The piercing tool was then isolated for 6 days, and a final CSVC extraction 3 was collected into a single 2-liter bottle with a final equilibration pressure of 5 x 10⁻⁴ Torr. All gas samples collected remain available to scientists to request for study, with the exception of the two small 50 cm³ bottles (see below).

The two 50 cm³ bottles of gas (OVC1; CSVC1) were subsampled and portions of each distributed for preliminary analyses to ANGSA Team members Dr. Zachary Sharp at the University of New Mexico and Dr. Rita Parai at Washington University in St. Louis [6-7]. Dr. Sharp's results showed that the vast majority of gas within both the OVC and CSVC is N₂, and thus there is little evidence for laboratory atmos-

phere contamination within the samples. The δ¹⁵N value of -4.4‰ relative to air is generally consistent with, albeit slightly lower than, the gas used in our N₂ purged cabinets, suggesting that ¹⁴N has preferentially leaked into the system from the cabinet. The CSVC sample has a lower absolute concentration of N₂ than the OVC sample (98.3% vs. 99.9%), suggesting that some of the H₂O, H₂, and Ar within the CSVC could be indigenous in origin (though some of the H₂ would have exsolved from the SS over the years of storage; see [7] for more details). Similarly, Dr. Parai's results for major gas phases measured by RGA showed that N₂ was the dominant gas (presumably curation cabinet gas), with measurable CO₂ and H₂ gas (likely exsolved from the SS containers), and no evidence of significant contamination of the OVC or CSVC gas from laboratory air. Additionally, although there was some evidence of a terrestrial component in some of the noble gas measurements from the CSVC1 sample, there was also clear evidence of a solar wind component apparent in both the Ne and Ar isotopes (see [6] for more details).

The gas extraction component of ANGSA worked well, and the ANGSA gas extraction manifold and piercing tool remain available for future gas extraction work on lunar samples. Using the existing piercing tool would be contingent upon future sealed containers fitting inside it, though a similar piercing tool designed to the specifications of the new sealed containers could be modeled after the existing tool (assuming the new containers are not valved).

References: [1] Shearer C. K. et al. (2024) *Space Sci Rev.* [10.1007/s11214-024-01094-x](https://doi.org/10.1007/s11214-024-01094-x). [2] Gross J. et al. (2025) *JGR Planets*, [10.1029/2024JE008585](https://doi.org/10.1029/2024JE008585). [3] Schmitt et al. (2017) *Icarus* 298, 2-33. [4] Alton J. H. (1989) *Apollo Tools Catalog*. [5] Butler P. (1973) *Apollo 17 Lunar Sample Information Catalog*. [6] Parai. R. et al. (2022) *Apollo 17 - ANGSA workshop*, abstract #2028. [7] Sharp et al. (2022) *Apollo 17 - ANGSA workshop*, abstract #2052.

Sample number		Container number	Container volume	Container press (Torr)	Type of gas in the container	Equilibration time	Notes
Generic	Specific						
73001	,5001	4	1.9 L	5 × 10 ⁻⁶	System Blank	15 min	
73001	,5002	3	1.9 L	27	OVC, 1st extraction	15 min	
73001	,5003	2	1.9 L	7	OVC, 2nd extraction	15 min	
73001	,5004	1	1.9 L	0.2	CSVC, Leak Gas 1	15 min	Accumulated in the piercing tool for 24 hr prior to extraction
73001	,5005	8	1.9 L	0.2	CSVC, Leak Gas 2	15 min	Accumulated in the piercing tool for 24 hr prior to extraction
73001	,5006	6	1.9 L	4.6	CSVC, 1st extraction	15 min	
73001	,5007	7	1.9 L	4.6	CSVC, 1st extraction	15 min	
73001	,5008	5	1.9 L	3.2	CSVC, 2nd extraction	10.75 days	
73001	,5009	9	1 L	5 × 10 ⁻⁴	CSVC, 3rd extraction	15 min	Piercing Tool/CSVC was pumped down to 2 × 10 ⁻⁷ Torr; gas accumulated in sealed piercing tool for 6 days prior to
73001	,5010	10	50 cc	28	OVC, 1st extraction	15 min	Consumed for PE
73001	,5011	11	50 cc	4.6	CSVC, 1st extraction	15 min	Consumed for PE